

THE EFFECT OF COKE CONSUMPTION ON LIPID PEROXIDASE AND ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE ACTIVITY IN THE SERUM AND LIVER OF *Rattus norvegicus*.

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ABSTRACT

The effect of coke also known as pop soda on lipid peroxidase activity and alkaline phosphatase activity in the serum and liver of *rattus norvegicus* upon consumption of coke was studied in this research. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of coke consumption on lipid peroxidase and alkaline phosphatase activity in the serum and liver of *rattus norvegicus*. The results from this study show that there was a statistically significant increase of lipid peroxidase. The result from the investigation of liver lipid peroxidase activities showed that there was an increase in lipid peroxidase activity ($5.88 \pm 1.45^*$) when compared with that of the control (5.04 ± 0.82). The results from the study of alkaline phosphatase activities revealed that the activities level of serum ALP of group B (15.90 ± 1.6) showed a significant decrease at ($P < 0.05$) when compared with that of the control A (18.38 ± 3.9) (Table 2). The implication of this result is that over consumption of coke may reduce the activities of alkaline phosphatase in the serum. However, this was not so for liver alkaline phosphatase as there was a significant increase in the activity of ALP ($27.50 \pm 1.7^*$) at ($P < 0.05$) when compared to the control (13.80 ± 2.0). This may be due to detoxification reaction taking place in the liver as a result of the consumption of coke.

KEYWORDS: Coke, carbonated drinks, liver, pop soda, *Rattus norvegicus*, lipid peroxidase and alkaline phosphatase.

INTRODUCTION

Carbonated drinks are soft drinks which contain carbon but do not contain alcohol, they are also known as soda pop. They have a sweet bubbly refreshing taste. They are commonly referred to as soda pop and contain mainly water, sugar and chemicals in the form of colorings, flavors, preservatives and sweeteners (Adjene et al, 2010).

Sucrose is the major sweetening agent in soft drink. It is a disaccharide that contains equal parts of the monosaccharide fructose and glucose. High fructose corn syrup, was later preferred to sucrose as the sweetener of choice in the soft drink industry, mainly because it is cheap to produce and can be engineered to contain varying amounts of glucose and fructose. It also extends the shelf life of products (Sandra, 2008; Bray et al., 2004). The fructose content of beverages sweetened with sugars range from 7% to 15% by weight (Drills, 1993).

In today's world, the liver receives more than its share of insults, from things like auto exhaust, secondhand smoke, pesticides, heavy metals, industrial solvents and household cleaners, not to mention over-the-counter prescription medication, food additives and various bacteria. These factors can prevent the liver from optimally performing the above listed functions. Other factors include excessive stress on the liver and poisons from other toxins. Several food items have been found to be harmful to the liver in various ways. For instance the calabash chalk which is commonly eaten by pregnant women has been found to cause fragmentation of the parenchyma cells of the liver of adult Wistar rats (Ekong et al., 2009). Heated and oxygenated corn oil oils have been found to cause depletion of glycogen and dilation of cisternae of rough endoplasmic reticulum and smooth endoplasmic reticulum (Shibayama, 1992).

The liver fraction is believed to be involved in the transport process and that the primary importance of measuring alkaline phosphatase is to check the possibility of bone or liver disease since the mucosal cells that

line the bile system of the liver are the source of alkaline phosphatase, the free flow of bile through the liver and down into the biliary tract and gall bladder are responsible for maintaining the proper level of this enzyme in the blood. When the liver, bile ducts or gall bladder system are not functioning properly or are blocked, this enzyme is not excreted through the bile hence alkaline phosphatase is released into the blood stream (Jeroh et al., 2012).

Consumption of soft drinks, carbonated beverages, in particular, has increased markedly in the past two decades to three decades (Nielson and Popkin, 2004; Harnack *et al.*, 1999).

Soft drink consumption has been linked with obesity, type -2 diabetes, dental caries, low nutrient levels, osteoporosis and has shown to increase the risk of metabolic syndrome (Nimeret *et al.*, 2008; Vartaman *et al.*, 2007; Malik *et al.*, 2006; Jurgens *et al.*, 2005; and Bray *et al.*, 2004).

Lipid peroxidation refers to the oxidative degradation of lipids. It is the process whereby free radicals 'steal' electrons from the lipids in the cell membranes, resulting to cell damage. This process proceeds by a free radical chain reaction mechanism. It most often affects polyunsaturated fatty acids, because they contain multiple double bonds in between which lies methylene -CH₂- groups that possess especially reactive hydrogen. As with any radical reaction, the reaction consists of three major steps: initiation, propagation and termination (Marnett, 1999).

The toxicity of lipid hydroperoxides to animals is best illustrated by the lethal phenotype of glutathione peroxidase 4, knockout mice. These animals do not survive past embryonic day 8, indicating that the removal of lipid hydroperoxides is absolutely essential for mammalian life (Muller *et al.*, 2007).

Individuals consuming more than one soft drink per day have a higher prevalence of the metabolic syndrome than those consuming less than one drink per day.

In Nigeria, about 60%-70% of babies are given soft drinks which include Coke, Pepsi, and Seven-Up at parties for refreshment or at home before meal.

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his study investigates the effect of coke on alkaline phosphatase activity and lipid peroxidase activity in the serum and liver of *Rattus novergicus* (Wister rat).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Animal care ethics:

Ten *Rattus novergicus* (Wister rats) of both sexes with average weight of 234g were randomly assigned into two groups A and B. Group A served as control while group B served as the treatment group. The rats were obtained and maintained in the Animal Holdings of the department of Anatomy, School of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Benin. The animals were fed with grower's mash obtained from Top feed limited, Sapele, Delta State. Two crates of coke were de-identified and branded. They were sourced from the coca cola and Pepsi mini depot in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Coke administration:

Rattus novergicus in the treatment groups A, were given 350ml of water while treatment group B were given 350ml of fresh bottled coke liberally, on a daily basis for thirty days. This was repeated twice daily with fresh bottled content. *R. novergicus* were then sacrificed by cervical dislocation on the thirty-first day of the experiment. 5ml of blood was collected and put in a test tube and spinned in a centrifuge for 15mins to obtain the serum and then the liver was quickly obtained and placed in ice to avoid enzyme denaturation. 0.5g of the obtained liver was homogenated with 10% normal saline for biochemical assay after the homogenates were centrifuged at high speed to separate the components.

Biochemical Assay:

The measurement of enzyme activity was done using the spectrophotometer.

Statistical Analysis:

The results were expressed as mean \pm SD. The student t-test was used for the evaluation of statistical significance. The results were judged significant if $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Coca-Cola is produced by the Coca-Cola Company in Atlanta Georgia. It is enjoyed by both old and young people alike but has found more popularity among youths and children. Despite its popularity and satisfaction, Coca-Cola has in recent time come under intense criticism from health professionals, Nutritionist and researchers; who claim that the product is a source of health concern (Jeroh *et al* 2012).

The consumption of carbonated drinks has been associated with obesity, type- 2 diabetes, dental caries, low nutrient level and osteoporosis (Vartamanet *al.*, 2007; Malik *et al.*,2006; Jurgens *et al.*,2005; and Bray *et al.*,2004).

Table 1: The activities of lipid peroxidase in serum and liver of *rattusnovergicus* after administration of 350ml coke.

Parameters	Control (A)	Treatment (B)
SerumLPA (µ/ml)	2.88±0.91	5.90±0.64*
Liver LPA (µ/ml)	5.04±0.83	5.88±1.45*

Values are mean±SD, n=5.

* represent significant differences of test groups in comparison with respective controls; at (P<0.05).

Table 2: The activities of alkaline phosphatase in serum and liver of *Rattus novergicus* after administration of 350ml coke.

Parameters	Control (A)	Treatment (B)
Serum ALP (U/L)	18.38±3.9	15.90±1.6
Liver ALP (U/L)	13.80±2.0	27.50±1.7*

Values are mean±SD, n=5.

* represent significant differences of test groups in comparison with respective controls; at (P<0.05).

The results from this study revealed that the activities of lipid peroxidation in serum, showed a significant increase (5.90±0.64*) at (P<0.05) when fed with 350ml of coke, when compared with that of the control A (2.88±0.91) (Table 1.). This may be due to the destruction of cell membrane which is involved in cellular processes such as cell adhesion, ion conductivity, cell signaling, and serving as attachment surface for the extra cellular glycocalyx, cell wall and intra cellular cytoskeleton. The destruction of this cell membrane proceed by a free radical chain reaction mechanism which lead to generation of oxygen free radical and reactive oxygen species such as hydroxyl radical and hydroperoxyl radicals which combine with hydrogen atom to form water and fatty acid radical which may result to haemolysis by rupturing red blood cell (Enrique *et al.*, 2008)/ Research has shown that coke consumption overwork the liver since it contains fructose which is only metabolized in the liver whereas glucose is metabolized by the body cells. This high stress has been found to trigger inflammation response in rat and increase lipid peroxidase; which disturb the pro-oxidant/anti-oxidant system of cells thereby leading to oxygen free radicals reactive oxygen species (Kelly *et al.*, 2003). Also previous study conducted showed that high fructose corn syrup which is a constituent of coca cola has been implicated in elevated blood cholesterol level and creation of blood clots; inhibit the action of white blood cells (Sanda, 2003).

The result from the investigation of liver lipid peroxidase activities showed that there was a little increase in lipid peroxidase activity (5.88±1.45*) when compared with that of the control (5.04± 0.82). This might have been as a result of glutathione peroxidase (GPX) which is an anti-oxidant that help reduce toxic hydrogen peroxide. GPX metabolizes lipidperoxidase in the liver (Kasamaet *al.*, 1998). This might be the reason for the absence of noticeable change in lipid peroxidase.

The results from the study of alkaline phosphatase activities revealed that the activities level of serum ALP of group B (15.90 ± 1.6) showed a significant decrease at ($P < 0.05$) when compared with that of the control A (18.38 ± 3.9) (Table 2). The implication of this result is that over consumption of coke may reduce the activities of alkaline phosphatase in the serum. However, this was not so for liver alkaline phosphatase as there was a significant increase in the activity of ALP ($27.50 \pm 1.7^*$) at ($P < 0.05$) when compared to the control (13.80 ± 2.0). This may be due to detoxification reaction taking place in the liver as a result of the consumption of coke.

CONCLUSION

This research has shown that over consumption of coke can lead to increase in activity of lipid peroxidase as a result of the destruction of cell membrane which is involved in cellular processes. However, it was observed that serum alkaline phosphatase activity was reduced on consumption of coke but increased significantly at the liver. This increase may be attributed to detoxification reaction in the liver.

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